

EFFECTIVE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND GAMIFICATION IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Bobomurodova Marjona Kamoljonovna

bobomurodovamarjona30@gmail.com

Akbarova Mohichehra Xurshid qizi

amohichehra@icloud.com

Students of the Uzbek State University of World Languages

Research supervisor: **Alikulova Shaxnoza Abdullo qizi**

Annotation. In today's developing society, much attention is given to teaching foreign languages and many researchers working on it. Especially, the opening of many private schools and the recruitment of highly qualified specialists in higher education for teaching foreign languages. This article examines, from a scientific perspective, the use of digital technologies and artificial intelligence- based technologies to enhance learning effectiveness and make it simple.

Keywords: digital technologies, gamification, foreign languages, online learning, online platforms, AI.

Аннотация. Сегодня, в быстро развивающемся обществе, особое внимание уделяется изучению иностранных языков, в результате чего проводится множество исследований. В частности, увеличивается количество специализированных школ, где студенты имеют возможность изучать иностранные языки у высококвалифицированных специалистов. В данной статье рассматривается использование цифровых технологий и инструментов на основе искусственного интеллекта в образовании для облегчения процесса обучения и повышения его эффективности, а также их преимущества, недостатки и факторы, устраняющие их с научной точки зрения.

Ключевые слова: современные технологии, геймификация, иностранные языки, онлайн-обучение, онлайн-платформы, ИИ.

Annotatsiya. Bugungi rivojlanib borayotgan jamiyatimizda, chet tillarini o'qitishga juda katta ahamiyat qaratilmoqda va bu yo'nalishda kopingina izlanishlar olib borilmoqda. Xususan, iqtisoslashgan maktablarning kopayishi va oliy ta'lim dargohlarida ham chet tillarini organish uchun o'z sohasining yuqori darajadagi mutaxassislari jalb qilinishi. Ushbu maqola ta'limda o'rganishni osonlashtirish va samaradorligini oshirish maqsadida raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellektga asoslangan vositalarning qo'llanishi, uning afzalliklari, kamchiliklari va ularni bartaraf etuvchi omillarni ilmiy nuqtai nazardan korib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy texnologiyalar, gamifikatsiya, xorijiy tillar, online o'rganish, online platformalar, AI.,

Nowadays, the issue of improving the quality of education is relevant worldwide, and great importance is being attached to teaching foreign languages using modern methods and technologies, and our state is making significant investment to improve the efficiency of teaching. Lots of students face difficulties with learning and using new languages in communication or daily life. Jane McGonigal, in her book "Reality is broken", Justified the need to introduce the "gamification" method, which was used by American programmer N. Pelling in 2002, into education as a solution[1]. What is gamification? Gamification is a method of activating human motivation and participation by applying game elements to non-

game situations. That is, we apply the elements found in the game (scoring/ reytng table/ difficulty levels/ incentives and rewards) to another process. This is precisely the aspect of digital technology dependence, that is, we can now observe an increasing dependence on the technology in every student, and with the gamification method, we encourage the to use mobile applications and gadgets more widely.

Many statistics have proven through various theories that tis is an effective method and a convenient means of children to achieve great success in education. While Deterding et al. and Manzano-Leon et al. have studied how this method can motivate students, recent researchers, Dehghanzadeh et al., Yu et al., and Zeybek & Saygı have examined the impact and effectiveness of gamification on children's learning based on a systematic review.

All of these studies support the gamification method and justify its necessity for learning. Deterding et al. conducted a systematic review of various articles and books and analyzed 173 articles[3]. In order to showing how it can effect and it's positive sides of students' attendance and behavior during the lesson. Exploring the impact of gamification on students' academic performance: A comprehensive meta-analysis of studies from the year 2008 to 2023. The purpose of the article to find a difference between the students academic performance and understanding, who studied with the modern teaching technologies and gamification with other students. What is the main purpose of the research? The primary focus is currently on education, and the largest database, unfortunately, is not in Uzbek, which is why the demand for learning foreign languages has increased. But which method is more effective? They came to the conclusion that it was necessary to know this and achieve results faster, and they conducted various studies on many methods. The result is a unique effect and achievement in each teaching method. We will examine the results of research conducted on gamification, a currently popular teaching method that uses digital tools alongside traditional teaching methods. Many scientists have come to a positive conclusion when examining the effects of gamification on behavioral change, learning, motivation, and academic performance. According to data from random-effect models, gamification has a significantly small but positive effect on cognitive ($g = .49$, 95% CI [0.30; 0.69], $k = 19$, $N = 1686$), motivational ($g = .36$, 95% CI [0.18; 0.54], $k = 16$, $N = 2246$), and behavioral learning outcomes ($g = .25$, 95% CI [0.04; 0.46], $k = 9$, $N = 951$)

The impact of gamification on cognitive learning outcomes was also consistent in a further analysis of studies with high methodological rigor. However, the impact on motivational and behavior outcomes was find less consistent[4].

As for research on digital technologies, there are many types(apps, online platforms, VR, AR, AI) and thematic areas like presence, engagement and personalization. Digital technologies, AI and online platforms are commonly used in learning new languages, and their effectiveness is clear in students' academic performance. If we analyze the effectiveness of artificial intelligence; it was observed that showed significant increase in students' academic performance. Also, according to the results of the experiment conducted at UniDistance Suisse, the exam scores of students who studied with the help of an LLM tutor grew by an average of 15%. Artificial intelligence not only provides knowledge to students, but also optimizes their learning way.[5] Online platforms are seen as a solution to the geographical and temporal problems faced by learners.

They have the opportunity to study conveniently, at any time and in any place, based on a flexible study plan. The use of modern technologies in lessons makes the learning process more interactive and interesting, which creates the necessary conditions for individual learning and motivation for language acquisition. For example, mobile applications such as

"duolingo", "quizzlet" help them understand and master the lessons; websites such as "Kahoot!" and "Bamboozle" help consolidate the knowledge they have acquired in the form of questions and answers. This method, unlike traditional education, creates a more interesting environment and healthy competition, encouraging students to work harder. Really, such children increase their internal motivation and intellectual potential.

Gamification is not simply a "stimulation" through games, but acts as a protective shield for the student, that is, it prevents fatigue, boredom, and distraction from lessons due to the reduced attention span among youngsters, and gives the brain a "break" signal without going out from the lesson.

In addition it makes it possible to improve four skills(reading, listening, speaking and writing) at the same time.digital technologies makes language learning more flexible, effective and interactive.[4].

Alternatively, this may have a negative effect on the learning process. First of all, students have different level of digital knowledge and some of them even do not know how to use them effectively. Educational initiatives must focus on promoting digital literacy alongside language learning. Additionally, over-reliance on technology can lead to laziness in language learning and the erosion of human factors, cultural immersion and interpersonal communication. A balanced approach that combines digital tools with traditional methods is seen as a comprehensive solution. While students can use digital applications and AI to organize and enhance their learning, they cannot replace real teachers. Because teaching based on artificial intelligence were not adapted to empathize with students, adapt to context, and encourage and motivate students to think critically. In generalized way, it can create cultural exchange, corporation and stable communicative competence. In other words, they can exchange ideas with their peers or make native friends, making language learning easier..

To conclude, if we used appropriately, digital technologies used in education will not only have a dramatic impact on language learning, but will also open up the possibilities of a multilingual world for us. The developing digital technologies, teaching process based on modern technologies and methods, and effective use of gamification make language learning more effective. It leads to way for closer integration into an interconnected communities. Integrating modern technologies and methods into education system for the new generation, providing that teaching methods keep up with the times, remains one of the pressing issues for specialists and scientists

References:

1. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1CAIS.04630>
2. The Gamification of Learning and Instruction — Kapp, K. M. (2012). The Gamification of Learning and Instruction. Pfeiffer.
3. <https://bera-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/toc/14678535/2024/55/6>
<https://www.springernature.com/gp/open-science/about/the-fundamentals-of-open-access-and-open-research> volume32, pages 77-112, (2020).
4. Deterding, S., Dixon, D., Khaled, R., & Nacke, L. (2011). "From Game Design Elements to Gamefulness: Defining Gamification." MindTrek Conference Proceedings.